

Effects of roller bending on curved constructional steels of rectangular hollow section

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Abstract

Curved steel members have seen much use in modern construction, constituting an attractive solution for architecturally exposed structural steel applications used in large span roofs, bridges, stadiums, atriums etc. Curved steels are manufactured from initially straight members, which are subjected to bending in order to achieve the desired curvature. Roller bending is a typical method of curving constructional steels using a 3-roller machine on hot finished steel sections; hollow sections employ the most difficult case, as, without the correct machinery to support internally the section's flanges, the process usually results in concavity distortion or even buckling. Significant residual stresses and reduction of the remaining ductility is encountered afterwards in curved members, which has not been investigated thoroughly in the literature. In this study, numerical models are developed in the finite element software ADINA, in order to simulate in detail the curving procedure along with the full interaction between the bending machine and the work pieces, accounting for geometric and material nonlinearities. By means of such models the effects of roller-bending on the locked-in stress and strain distributions of various steel hollow-sections are examined and the influence of the major curving parameters, such as the cross-sectional shape factor, the yield stress, the bending radius, the roller-bending arrangement and the filling of the hollow section's cavity with mandrels is quantified.

Keywords: Steel arches; Rectangular hollow sections; Residual stresses, Roller bending; Cold-forming; Curving process; nonlinear finite element analysis

1. Introduction

Architecturally Exposed Structural Steel (AESS) has become more and more popular worldwide, as a way of expressing the structural integrity of a building and at the same time putting the structural system at the aesthetic forefront. AESS is commonly associated with the use of curved structural steel members due to their aesthetic appeal and the variety of forms that can be created. Curved steel structures are also designed to provide the users of the structure with natural light and a sense of spaciousness. Typical examples of curved steel elements can be seen in large span roofs, bridges, stadiums, atriums etc. (Fig.1).

Figure 1: Curved steel elements used at AESS applications.

Curved steel members don't just "come that way" from the mill but are manufactured from initially straight members which are subjected to bending in order to meet the desired curvature [1, 2]. Steel members are usually curved by roller-bending or induction-bending methods, constituting cold-formed and thermally treated processes respectively. The "Roller bending" or "Pyramid rolling" method as it is also called because of the bending machine's pyramid arrangement (Fig. 2 left), is the most common method of curving constructional steels where a steel member passes iteratively through three rollers, causing plastic deformations along its entire length. In each subsequent iteration, the roller in the middle moves towards the other two, in order to adjust the applied curvature. In induction bending (Fig. 2 right), the member is passed through an electric coil causing deformations within the heated zone, while a pivoted radius arm controls the applied rotation. The induction process is generally more expensive than the cold-formed process, although smaller radii can be achieved and lighter sections can be curved. The different processes produce different finishes, depending on the member, the material and the radius.

Figure 2: Roller-bending (left) and induction-bending (right) machines for curving constructional steel.

The minimum allowed radius of curvature is limited by the maximum magnitude of cross-sectional distortion which may take place during bending process. Auxiliary rolls are used on the tension flanges of open cross-sections in order to provide additional restraint against local flange bending and web buckling. Roller bending of hollow sections is even more challenging since curving at tight radii or similarly bending rectangular tubes with thin walls usually results in concavity distortion. Roller bending companies often facilitate the procedure with filling the hollow section cavity with mandrels in order to internally restrain the flanges. Rectangular hollow section steel elements can be bent either the "hard way", about the strong axis, or the "easy way", about the weak axis. Even though more pressure is required to produce a bend the hard way, the resulting curved rectangular tube is less likely to distort precisely because it is more rigid than a section curved the easy way.

The roller bending process induces significant local deformations and residual stresses, as most of the section exhibits yielding. The encountered locked-in stresses affect the overall behavior, inducing premature yielding of the cross-section and having considerable effect on the brittle fracture, fatigue and buckling strength [3]. The way in which residual stresses influence the behavior depends on their distribution over the cross-section, which is considerably different in the case of curved members than in straight members [4]. A theoretical model for providing the residual stress distribution after curving has been proposed by Timoshenko [5], as a function of the steel's yield stress f_y and the ratio α between the plastic and elastic section modulus; the proposed model is based on the Euler-Bernoulli beam theory by aggregating uniaxial stresses from inelastic bending and elastic spring-back, as shown in Fig. 3. Spoorenberg et al. [6-8] have carried out residual stress measurements on roller-bent wide flange sections using the sectioning method, along with finite element simulations which concluded on a residual stress model for wide flange sections. A small-scale parametric study, concerning roller-bent elements of rectangular hollow section, has been performed by Chiew et al. [9], including parameters such as the rolling boundary conditions, the bending ratio, the steel yield stress and the cross-sectional dimensions. However, the influence of important parameters such as the shape factor α , the roller-bending arrangement and the filling with mandrels has not been assessed in the literature.

Figure 3: Theoretical residual stress distribution for roller-bent RH sections proposed by Timoshenko.

2. Numerical modeling of roller-bending

Realistic distributions of the developed residual stresses and plastic strains encountered on curved structural steels can be obtained by either numerical analyses or experimental measurements. In this study, finite element analyses were employed in order to simulate accurately the roller-bending process of initially straight beam segments of rectangular hollow section (RHS) and to extract the locked-in stress and strain distributions at the end of the procedure. Straight beam segments of total length 3m were modeled with a uniform and sufficiently dense mesh of 4-node shell elements with five integration points in the element thickness direction, in order to simulate reliably the elastoplastic behavior of the RHS thin-walled plates. Additionally, 4-node shell elements associated with an elastic steel material model, were used to model the cylindrical surfaces of the rollers; a typical bending machine arrangement of 300 mm roller diameter and a distance between the centers of the outer rollers equal to 900 mm was assumed. Rigid elements were used to connect the nodes of each cylinder to its center, in order to provide sufficient rigidity and to apply afterwards the prescribed displacements and rotations. Appropriate contact elements were introduced between the contacting interfaces of the rollers and the beam. The Coulomb friction coefficient of the contacting surfaces was taken equal to 0.3. Advantage was taken of symmetry conditions and the model's size was reduced to the half. Large strain and displacement formulations were employed for the Geometry and Material Nonlinear Analyses (GMNA), since local web buckling was critical and the developed plastic strains were significant. Implicit static analyses were carried out using the Newton – Raphson solution algorithm for the geometric and material nonlinear equations and the rigid target algorithm, which is mainly used for metal-forming applications, was employed for the solution of the nonlinear contact-element equations. The analysis sequence is illustrated schematically in Fig. 4, where a prescribed displacement at the middle roller is applied first towards the beam, followed by a prescribed rotation at the center of one roller (i.e the middle one); through contact traction, the beam is feded entirely, causing uniform plastification and locked-in stresses to the cross-section.

Figure 4: Numerical simulation of the roller-bending process.

3. Locked-in stress and strain distributions

In this section, the effects of roller-bending on the locked-in stress and strain distributions of RHS curved constructional steels are examined by performing a relevant parametric study. Detailed numerical simulations of the curving procedure for various RHS sections of different cross-sectional shape factor α , yield stress f_y , bending ratio R/h between the curvature radius R at the end of the curving process and the section height h , roller bending arrangement and either filling or not the sectional cavity with mandrels are performed in the finite element software ADINA [10]. Results of locked-in stress and strain distributions are depicted next. For better management of available space and exploiting symmetry, results are shown for one half of each RHS section.

3.1. Influence of cross-sectional shape factor α

The cross-sectional shape factor α , defined by the ratio between the plastic and elastic section modulus, is theoretically correlated with the amount of the residual stresses encountered at the RHS flanges after curving. In this section, straight constructional steel beams of different cross-sections and exhibiting a range of shape factors α from 1.157 to 1.270, shown in Table 1, typical of commercially available RHS, were modeled and curved either the “hard way” or the “easy way”. A bilinear, elastic-fully plastic material model of S355 steel grade was employed for the analyses. Results of the longitudinal residual stresses and accumulated plastic strains are shown in Fig. 5. A non-symmetrical layout of residual stresses and strains is obtained over the cross-sectional width and height; highest stress and strain values are located near the web middle ($\sim f_y$), as expected according to Timoshenko theory, and also at the edges of the bottom flange. It can be also seen that for the same sectional shapes (same bending ratios), increase of the thickness or accordingly increase of the shape factor, results in lower longitudinal stress and plastic strains on the web to flange junctions, while the web locked-in stresses are unaffected.

Table 1: Examined RH Sections and corresponding shape factors α .

RH Section	α	RH Section	α	RH Section	α
50x100x4	1.157	80x80x4	1.182	80x80x6	1.211
80x120x5	1.159	100x100x6	1.194	100x100x8	1.217
80x120x6	1.173	80x80x5	1.196	120x120x10	1.221
50x100x5	1.180	80x120x8	1.201	120x80x6	1.228
120x120x6	1.182	120x120x8	1.201	120x80x8	1.249
100x100x5	1.182	50x100x6	1.202	120x80x10	1.270

Figure 5: Longitudinal residual stresses and accumulated plastic strains for different shape factors α .

3.2. Influence of steel yield stress f_y

The magnitude of the residual stresses encountered in roller-bent steel members is theoretically related with the steel yield stress f_y . The effect of different steel grade on the residual stress and strain distributions is assessed for the RH sections 50x100x5, 80x80x6 and 120x80x8; these sections were selected to exhibit characteristic values of the cross-sectional factors α from the whole value range. A bilinear, elastic-fully plastic material model of steel corresponding to three different grades, namely S355, S275 and S235, was employed for the numerical analyses. Results of the longitudinal residual stresses and accumulated plastic strains for the different steel grades and cross sections are shown in Fig. 6. As expected, steel with a higher yield stress encounters higher residual stresses, while the effect of the steel grade on the plastic strains is found to be negligible.

Figure 6: Longitudinal residual stresses and accumulated plastic strains for different steel grades.

3.3. Influence of bending ratio R/h

The bending ratio R/h is associated with the amount of required work during bending and is proportionally related to the developed longitudinal strains according to the fundamental strain-curvature relationship, assuming that plane sections remain plane. The effect of the bending ratio R/h on the residual stress and strain distributions for the characteristic cross-sections RHS 50x100x5, 80x80x6 and 120x80x8 of S355 grade, is assessed. Results of the longitudinal residual stresses and accumulated plastic strains for various bending ratios and cross-sections are depicted in Fig. 7. It can be seen that increase of the bending ratio results in lower longitudinal stresses on the web to flange junctions, while the web locked-in stresses are unaffected. Furthermore, increase of the bending ratio results also in increase of the developed plastic strains, as expected.

Figure 7: Longitudinal residual stresses and accumulated plastic strains for different bending ratios.

3.4. Influence of roller-bending arrangement

The geometric characteristics of the roller-bending machine, such as the rollers diameter and the distance between them, affects both the developed bending moment and the length of plastic zone on the beam segment, and thus a different manipulation of the middle roller is required in every case. Aiming at assessing the influence of the pyramid arrangement on the locked-in stress and strains distributions, parametric analyses employing four different bending machine arrangements are carried out. Firstly, the distance between the centers of the outer rollers is kept constant (0.90m), while the rollers diameter is varied between 0.20m and 0.40m. Secondly, the distance between the centers of the outer rollers ranges between 0.70m and 1.10m, while the roller diameter remains constant (0.30m). The obtained locked-in stresses and the developed plastic strains concerning the RHS120x80x8 of steel grade S355, curved with the aforementioned bending arrangements, are depicted in Fig. 8. In order to achieve the same radii of curvature with the various arrangements, different manipulation of the middle-roller displacement was required. It can be seen that the roller diameter has a negligible effect on the locked-in stress and strain distributions, in contrast to the roller distance, where for longer bending machines lower stress concentration and developed strains are encountered at the web to flange junctions. This effect is attributed to the reduction of the shear forces with the increase of bending length.

Figure 8: Longitudinal residual stresses and accumulated plastic strains for different roller-bending arrangements.

3.5. Influence of mandrel filling

As with almost all metal bending processes, curving at tight radii or similarly bending rectangular tubes with thin walls, is limited by significant cross-sectional distortions that may take place (provided the

bending machine has the power to curve the sections). Aiming at minimizing the occurring distortions without increasing the thickness of the material, roller-benders often facilitate the procedure with filling the hollow section cavity with mandrels in order to internally restrain the RHS flanges. The effect of this technique on the developed locked-in stress and strain distributions is assessed in this section. To that end, a suitable numerical model is developed, employing spring elements to connect the corresponding nodes of the top and bottom flanges of the beam segment as is shown in Fig. 9 (left). The spring elements act on their deformed longitudinal direction, following a nonlinear constitutive law as shown in Fig. 9 (right) in order to contribute realistically in compression and not in tension as in the case of mandrels; the element-death feature of ADINA is employed in order to remove the spring elements before extracting the results.

Figure 9: Detail of the FE model with spring elements (left) and nonlinear constitutive law of springs (right).

The obtained locked-in stress and the developed plastic strains for the characteristic cross-sections RHS 50x100x5, 80x80x6 and 120x80x8 of S355 steel, which have either been filled with mandrels or not, are compared in Fig. 10. It can be seen that the mandrel filling results in a reduction of the residual stresses at both the web middle and the web to flange junction. Even more significant is the reduction of the developed plastic strains with the use of mandrels and thus the member's remaining ductility is positively affected.

Figure 10: Longitudinal residual stresses and accumulated plastic strains with or without mandrel filling.

4. Conclusions

A detailed finite element simulation methodology of the roller-bending procedure has been developed in the present study, capable of estimating the residual stress and strain formations of rectangular hollow sections after curving. Numerical analyses were performed in the finite element software ADINA accounting for the full interaction between the bending machine and the work pieces, as well as geometric and material nonlinearities. The influence of the major curving parameters, such as the cross-sectional shape factor, the yield stress, the bending radius, the roller-bending arrangement and the filling

of the hollow section's cavity with mandrels have been examined by a comprehensive parametric study. In all cases, non-symmetrical layouts of residual stress and strain are obtained over the cross-sectional width and height; stress and strain concentrations are located at the web middle ($\sim f_y$), as expected according to Timoshenko theory, and also at the edges of the bottom flange. Steel with a higher yield stress encounters higher residual stresses while the effect of the steel grade on the plastic strains is found to be negligible. Increase of the material thickness or accordingly of the shape factor results in lower longitudinal stress and plastic strains on the web to flange junctions, while the web locked-in stresses are unaffected. Increase of the bending ratio results in lower longitudinal stresses on the web to flange junctions, while the web locked-in stresses remain unaffected and the developed plastic strains are increased. The roller diameter has a negligible effect on the locked-in stress and strain distributions, in contrast to the roller distance, where for larger bending machines lower stress concentration and developed strains are encountered at the web to flange junctions. This effect is attributed to the reduction of the shear forces with the increase of bending length. Finally, the mandrel filling results in a reduction of the residual stresses at both the web middle and the web to flange junction. Even more significant is the reduction of the developed plastic strains with the use of mandrels and thus the member's remaining ductility is positively affected. In a subsequent step of this research, numerical analyses of roller-bent members with residual stresses will be carried out in order to quantify the effect of such stresses and strains on the members' response under service loads.

Acknowledgements

This research has been supported by the OptArch project: "Optimization Driven Architectural Design of Structures" (No: 689983) belonging to the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE) H2020-MSCA-RISE-2015.

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